

The Study of Gender Role Socialization Between The Major Female Characters in Tennessee William's The Glass Menagerie

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ABSTRACT

According to Feminism Theory the society has been dominated by patriarchal ideology, an ideology which positioned men as the superior group and women as the subordinate group. Women in society mostly have been positioned as inferior almost in every institutions such as social, economic, law, education, health, and religion. Due to literature is a product of the society, feminists believe that a literary work has a possibility in adopting patriarchal ideology and provides important proves on the process of patriarchal ideology socialization within the society.

The Glass Menagerie as one canon in literary work, written by Tennessee Williams during 1940-1941, has a possibility to carry the idea of gender concept as one product of patriarchal ideology. There is a tendency that the author has adopted gender values and socialized its to the society by using the description of gender role socialization process between the female characters in his work. This literary work has been chosen since this study aims to find out and analyze the possibility of gender role socialization process within a mother-daughter relationship as been described in this work. This study has used gender analysis, a gender perception that emphasized that motherhood can be the primary institution in patriarchal society in socializing patriarchal ideology and its values in form of gender roles, which caused the differentiation of societal roles between men and women. Feminism approach here is used since this approach has focused on the gender analysis on women in literary study. As a result, it is proved that there is a description of gender role socialization within mother-daughter relationship, that Amanda has been socialized certain gender roles explicitly to Laura, by using specific ways in socializing those gender roles.

Keywords: *gender role, patriarchal ideology, feminism.*

INTRODUCTION

Society where people live in right now, like any other historical civilization, is dominated by patriarchy. Patriarchal values in patriarchal society dominate every avenue of power within the society, including literature as a reflection of human life.

Since literature is a true reflection or mirror of human life, as stated by Kate Millet, many feminists consider that literature offers important evidence to the readers about how patriarchal society influences its members to socialize the gender role through the certain institution within the society. *The Glass Menagerie* a the object of analysis in this study has been chosen since this literary work is a male produced literature that might have the idea of gender role concept within the work (Djajanegara, 2001:18-19). There are two female major characters in this story, Amanda Wingfield as a dominant mother, and Laura Wingfield as a daughter. Amanda Wingfield here socializes the gender role toward her daughter Laura, using their mother-daughter relationship. The way in which Amanda socializes the gender role toward her daughter Laura is possible to be analyzed by using a gender analysis based on

Laurie Arliss' theory, especially social learning theory, as a feminism approach in literary work.

The main problem in this study are formulated into questions: What are the kinds of gender roles that Amanda socializes toward her daughter Laura in this play? How does Amanda socialize the gender roles toward her daughter Laura within their mother-daughter relationship?

LITERARY REVIEW

Mother as Patriarchal Agents in Doing Gender Role Socialization: Laurie Arliss

Arliss in her book *Gender Communication* (1991) says that parents are the primary socializer agents of patriarchal society when doing the process of gender role socialization, since they were the first agents of society who entered the children's life since they were born.

There are five basic consumptions as results of her research:

- 1) *Children often show a range of behaviors, some of which their parents react to and some of which they ignore.*

Since the child was born, parents tend to react differently toward their child's behaviors, baby boy or baby girl. Arliss states that there are typical traits of male and female that considered by parents as the appropriate behaviors for the babies, such as 'strong, solid, and independent' for baby boys and 'loving, cute, and sweet' for baby girls.

- 2) *Parents react to the child's behaviors if the behaviors are appropriate according to their conception of what the two sex-specific behaviors are like.*

Related to the 1st assumptions, parents will react to certain behaviors of their children, especially the sex-appropriate behaviors of their child. The reactions of parents as stated above start the process of selectively sanctioning behaviors of their children.

- 3) *In some cases, parents sometimes prepare their children for the appropriate adult sex roles purposely.*

Parents take some responsibilities in teaching boys and girls how to behave according to standard established by the society. The gender-specific toys that are assumed by parents as the sanctions of their child's behaviors considered as the preparatory for adult sex roles. The boys will be encouraged to play with masculine toys such as toy soldiers, trucks, cars, sport equipments, and building tools. The girls will be surrounded by dolls and miniature kitchen tools. The differentiation of these toys actually indicates the role division for male and female. This condition is called *anticipatory socialization* (Arliss, 1991:133).

- 4) *In other cases, parents may show the differential treatment of boys and girls about their behaviors, in terms of immediate concerns.*

In doing a socialization process, parents often respond to the behaviors of their children if they think it is appropriate for their sex, but act differently if the other children from different sex have the same behaviors. This condition is called as *non-anticipatory socialization* (Arliss, 1991:134).

- 5) *Parents tend to offer positive sanctions to sex-appropriate behaviors, and negative sanctions to sex-inappropriate behaviors.*

Parents will react positively and encouraging, and offer positive sanctions to their children if the children behave appropriately according to their sex, based on the conception or understanding of parents, or based on societal standards about sex-appropriate behaviors.

The positive sanction could be in verbal sanctions or in material things. Parents also will react negatively if their children behave inappropriately according to their sex-gender behavior, and the negative sanctions could also vary, but mostly in verbal sanctions or physical punishment.

Motherhood as Patriarchal institutions in Doing Gender Role Socialization Process: Adrienne Rich

Rich states that motherhood is not only as the experience of women as becoming mothers, but also as the patriarchal institution since the mothers are doing the job division based on sex differences and doing the process of gender role socialization to their children. She believes that biological motherhood can be as institution lying under the patriarchal society, which aim is to ensure that all potential in earth, and including women, shall remain under male control (Rich by Humm, 1992:269).

Rich argues that woman who have already being the society agents of patriarchy, when they are becoming mothers, will always do a process of gender role socialization to their children, especially to the daughter. So the process of gender role socialization of the daughters continues until adult. When the daughters are grown up and become mothers too, they will also do the process of gender role socialization to their children because they have it in their life since they were born –socialized by their mothers- and therefore placed their daughters in the subordinate position, where male will always be the center or the purpose on their life.

ANALYSIS

Gender Role Socialization

Parents sometimes prepare their children for the appropriate adult sex roles purposely.

Arliss assumes that in that in the absence of one parent, the rest of parents may assume having the same powerful position in relation to the child's gender role socialization. Here in this play, as a single parent, Amanda is very dominant in her family. Amanda prepares herself and her daughter, Laura, for the purpose of finding a husband for Laura. Here Amanda's job as a patriarchal institution is to socialize the role as a housewife to Laura.

1. Amanda socializes the role of a housewife through her advises to Laura

In Amanda's society, a young lady should have gentlemen caller, which is a young man who has a change to having a serious relationship, engage, and become her husband someday. Amanda then advises her daughter to prepare herself for a gentlemen caller too.

AMANDA. Resume your seat, little sister – I want you to stay fresh and pretty – for gentlemen callers!

[William in Dell Pub. Co., 1956:441, Scene One]

AMANDA ... Stay fresh and pretty! – It's almost time for our gentlemen callers to start arriving.

[William in Dell Pub. Co., 1956:443, Scene One]

AMANDA [*hopelessly fingering the huge pocketbook*]. So what are we going to do the rest of our lives? Stay home and watch the parades go by? ... What is there left but dependency all of our lives? I know so well what becomes of unmarried women who aren't prepared for occupy a position. ... Of course, some girls *do marry!*

[William in Dell Pub. Co., 1956:448, Scene Two]

AMANDA. Girls that's aren't cut out for business careers usually wind up married to some nice man. [*Gets up with a spark of revival.*] Sister, that's what you'll do!

[William in Dell Pub. Co., 1956:449, Scene Two]

Amanda emphasizes that a young girl like Laura should marry somebody, especially because Laura does not prepared herself for a permanent occupation. She even determines what behavior Laura should have in order to make young men attracted to her.

AMANDA. I understood the art of conversation!

TOM. I bet you could talk.

Amanda. Girls in those days knew how to talk, I can tell you.

.....
AMANDA. They knew how to entertain their gentlemen callers. It wasn't enough for a girl to be possessed of a pretty face and a graceful figure – although I wasn't slighted in either respect. She also needed to have nimble wit and a tongue to meet all occasions.

TOM. What did you talk about?

AMANDA. Things of importance going in the world! Never anything coarse or common or vulgar. ... My callers were gentlemen – all!

[William in Dell Pub. Co., 1956:441-442, Scene One]

Here, when the Wingfield family is having dinner, again Amanda advices Laura to masters the art of conversation because young lady cannot always count on their pretty face and graceful figure to attract men, but also has to be a good conversation partner for her gentlemen callers.

Amanda also emphasizes, that a young lady should not have a shy nature and stay in home most of her time.

AMANDA ... Laura, are you going to do what I asked you to do, or do I have to get dressed and go out myself?

LAURA. ... Butter and what else?

AMANDA ... Just better. Tell them to charge it.

LAURA. Mother, they make such faces when I do that.

AMANDA. Sticks and stones can break our bones, but the expression on Mr. Garfinkel's face won't harm us!

[William in Dell Pub. Co., 1956:458, Scene Four]

Amada advises Laura that she should not get nervous or shy while she interacts with somebody else. She cannot understand why Laura is too shy and why she cannot develop charm and vivacity like what she wants. She fails to see that Laura has different personality and character to her.

AMANDA [*impatiently*]. Why are you trembling?

LAURA. Mother, you've made me so nervous!

AMANDA. How have I made me nervous?

LAURA. By all this fuss! You make it seem so important!

AMANDA. I don't understand you, Laura. You couldn't be satisfied with just sitting home, and yet whenever I try to arrange something for you, you seem to resist it.

[William in Dell Pub. Co., 1956:475-476, Scene Six]

When she help Laura get dressed for a gentlemen caller who will arrive soon with Tom, Amanda once cannot understand why Laura becomes so nervous, instead of being excited and developing her charm and vivacity better just like her self when she was young in Blue Mountain. She says that Laura should not be satisfied with her life by just sitting home, taking care of her glass menagerie and old photograph records (Laura's favorite things to do most of her time).

2. Amanda socializes the role of a housewife through actions to Laura

Not only advises, Amanda also prepares Laura for the role as a housewife candidate that suitable for gentleman caller like Jim O'Connor, through her actions on Laura's performance.

[LAURA *stands in the middle with lifted arms while Amanda crouches before her, adjusting the hem of the new dress, devout and ritualistic. The dress is colored and designed by memory. The arrangement of LAURA's hair is changed; it is softer and more becoming. A fragile, unearthly prettiness has come out in LAURA: she is like a piece of translucent glass touched by light, given a momentary radiance, not actual, not lasting.*]

[William in Dell Pub. Co., 1956:475, Scene Six]

[AMANDA produces two powder puffs which she wraps in handkerchiefs and stuffs in LAURA's bosom]

LAURA. Mother, what are you doing?

AMANDA. They call them "Gay Deceiver"!

LAURA. I won't wear them!

AMANDA. You will!

LAURA. Why should I?

AMANDA. Because, to be painfully honest, your chest is flat.

[William in Dell Pub. Co., 1956:475-476, Scene Six]

Amanda determines what clothes are appropriate for Laura. She arranges Laura's hair, and as the result Laura becomes different, with an impression of fragile and unearthly prettiness. Amanda also adds two pieces of powder puffs to Laura's chest, to make her appearance more attractive to Mr. O'Connor. All that perfect preparation arranged by Amanda aims to prepare her daughter Laura for the gentleman caller, hope that their relationship can be continued seriously to become husband and wife.

3. Amanda prepares a housewife role for Laura through plans

In order to accomplish the obsession of a husband for Laura, Amanda involves Tom to help her in arranging a plan for Laura.

AMANDA. You have five minutes. I want to talk to about Laura.

[LEGEND: "PLANS AND PROVISIONS."]

... We have to making plans and provisions for her. She's older than you, two years, and nothing has happened. She just drifts along doing nothing. It frightens me terribly how just drifts along doing nothing. It frightens me terribly how she just drifts along ... I mean that as soon as Laura has got somebody to take care of her, married, a home for her own, independent. – ... I say for your sister because she's young and independent. I put her in business college – a dismal failure! ... I took her over to the Young People's League at the church. Another fiasco. She spoke to nobody, nobody spoke to her. Now all she does is fool with those pieces of glass and play those worn-out records. What kind of a life is that for a girl to lead?

[William in Dell Pub. Co., 1956:462-463, Scene Four]

From Amanda's conversation with Tom, it seems that Amanda thinks Laura cannot handle everything right by her self. All her efforts for Laura's better life seem to end with failure. Worried about Laura's empty life, she insists to involve Tom in her plan to look for a husband for Laura, somebody to love her and take care of her.

AMANDA. I remember suggesting that it would be nice for your sister if you brought home some nice young man from the warehouse. I think that I've made that suggestion more than once.

TOM. Yes, you have made it repeatedly.

[William in Dell Pub. Co., 1956:467, Scene Five]

From Tom's word in his dialogue '*repeatedly*', it is very clear that Amanda again and again forces her son to help her finding a 'gentleman caller' for Laura. It is strongly emphasized by Amanda's saying '*more than once*' about her plan for Laura. Amanda hopes that Laura someday will become an independent woman, but she forces he daughter to marry somebody. It means that Laura still needs a male figure to help her face her life and be dependent to her husband someday.

In Scene Six, when the gentleman caller arrives, Amanda talks like it was Laura who prepared all the perfect preparation for dinner.

AMANDA. Honey, you go ask Sister if the supper is ready! You know that Sister is in full of charge of supper!

.... It's rare for a girl as sweet an' pretty as Laura to be domestic! But Laura is, thank heavens, not only pretty but also very domestic.

[William in Dell Pub. Co., 1956:485, Scene Six]

When Amanda greets O'Connor, she emphasizes that Laura takes all responsibility for the dinner preparation. She states clearly that Laura is not only pretty but also very domestic, not like any other girl (notice the word '*rare for a girl*'). The dialogue above supports the interpretation that Amanda wants to make sure that her plan for Laura goes well, by creating the best impression for Laura as a perfect candidate for a housewife.

AMANDA. Laura – rest on the sofa. Well! [To *the gentleman caller*.] ... Standing over the hot stove made her ill! – I told her that it was just too warm this evening, but –

[William in Dell Pub. Co., 1956:486, Scene Six]

Amanda does not want her perfect plan to end with failure again because Laura suddenly falls sick because of her over nervous nature, but she also takes it as the perfect situation to support her plan. After she asks Laura to get rest on the sofa in the living room, instead of explaining to Jim why Laura is suddenly sick, she explains to Jim that it might be a temporarily sick because of a hot temperature of a stove, when Laura cooked dinner.

Parents tend to offer positive sanctions to sex-appropriate behaviors, and negative sanctions to sex-inappropriate behaviors

According to Arliss, parents tend to offer sanctions, depends on the behaviors of their children. The negative sanctions are given to sex-appropriate behaviors and positive sanctions are given to sex-appropriate behaviors. The positive sanctions can be in form of material things or positive words, and negative sanctions mostly in form of verbal sanctions, body expression and gesture, prohibition, or physical punishment. (Arliss, 1991:133-135). In this play, Amanda tends to offer negative sanctions to Laura instead of positive sanctions. This is related to her nature, extremely domineering her children, constantly putting them down and making them feel as if they were inferior and could not do anything right by making decisions for them, allowing them to decide little regarding their own future.

Amanda offers negative sanctions to Laura through expression. Amanda often notices her children's weaknesses and failures in their life, especially Laura, instead of trusting her to have her own decision about her life and her future. After Laura drops out of business school, Amanda becomes very pessimistic about her future, and afraid that she will become an "old maid" someday. Besides strongly advises her about find a husband, Amanda also offers negative sanctions to Laura in form of her expression, aims to rise Laura's guilty because she cannot accomplish her mother's hope, preparing herself for an occupation, and for a husband.

[... seeing her mother's expression, LAURA touches her lips with a nervous gesture.]

[AMANDA leans against the shut door and stares at LAURA with a martyred look.]

... Why? Why? How old are you, Laura?

LAURA. Mother, you know my age.

AMANDA. I thought that you were an adult; it seems that I was mistaken. [She crosses slowly to the sofa and sinks down and stares to LAURA.]

LAURA. Please don't stare at me, Mother.

[William in Dell Pub. Co., 1956:445, Scene Two]

The conversation above shows that Laura becomes nervous because of her mother's disappointed expression. And by asking Laura's age, it is just the same as directly putting Laura down and making her feel inferior and could not do anything right. It implies in Amanda's question about Laura's age, that Laura has done such a thing that was not appropriate with her age as an adult person. Amanda's disappointed feeling emphasizes by her face expression, staring at Laura, to raise guilty feeling of her daughter.

LAURA. Mother, when you're disappointed, you get that awful suffering look on your face, like the picture of Jesus' mother in the museum! ... I couldn't face it.

[William in Dell Pub. Co., 1956:447, Scene Two]

Laura says that she actually cannot stand with Amanda's awful suffering look, when she was disappointed of Laura's behavior. And it makes her feels guiltier than before because she is considered as immature adult person by her mother, could not do anything right in her own life and prepare herself for her own future.

Amanda offers negative sanctions to Laura through negative words. Being a forceful and dominant mother, who always arranges everything for her children and does not trust her children to make own decision about their life, especially for Laura, Amanda offers sanctions Laura negatively by saying negative words if she thinks Laura's behaviors are inappropriate regarding her role as a young lady. In scene six, Amanda helps Laura to prepare herself for a dinnertime with a gentleman caller. But she becomes so impatiently because Laura is very nervous and trembling, instead of having fun and excited to have a dinnertime with a young man. She cannot understand why Laura does not seriously take one important moment in a life of a young lady like her, to have gentleman caller.

AMANDA. I don't intend to humor silliness, Laura. I've had too much from you and your brother, both!

[William in Dell Pub. Co., 1956:478]

Here Amanda becomes impatient with Laura's nervous nature. She consider Laura's act as silly behavior. From her saying to Laura "*I've had too much from you and your brother, both!*" seems that Amanda wants to emphasize that her life is "full" with effort to survive in life with two children who act very silly all the time, and right now they should not act silly again, especially Laura, considering that this is a very special moment for Laura. The next moment, after knowing that the "mysterious guest" is actually O'Connor, Laura's dream man since she were in high school, Laura refuses to meet O'Connor, Laura's refusal makes Amanda become impatient again and get irritated because she has arranged a perfect "first impression" for Laura and Jim O'Connor by giving Laura job to open the door and greet her gentleman caller.

AMANDA [*in a fierce whisper*]. What is the matter with you, you silly thing? ... I told you I wasn't humor you, Laura. Why have you chosen this moment to lose your mind?

[William in Dell Pub. Co., 1956:479-480]

Amanda thinks Laura's over nervous nature is a silly behavior, considering that it is a very special and important moment for their family to have "the one and only" dinnertime

with Laura's gentleman caller. When Amanda cannot hold her impatient emotion, she calls her daughter as a "silly thing", because Laura cannot control her nervous and disturbs her mother's perfect plan for her.

Amanda offers negative sanctions to Laura through prohibition. Amanda wants her daughter to develop charm and vivacity like she once when she was young in Blue Mountain, popular girl with her seventeen gentleman callers. Amanda refuses to see that Laura is limp, and her limp becomes her huge stumbling block to interact normal with other people.

LAURA [in a tone of frightened apology]. I'm – crippled!

AMANDA. Nonsense! Laura, I've told you never, never to use that word. Why, you're not crippled, you just have a little defect – hardly noticeable, even!

[William in Dell Pub. Co., 1956:449, Scene Two]

From Amanda's words, she strongly forbids her daughter to say the word "*crippled*", pretends that Laura only has a little defect, pretends that her limp supposedly not become a burden for Laura to develop her charm and vivacity like what Amanda has expected. From Laura's tone when she says about her defect condition, *frightened apology*, it can be interpreted that Laura also consider herself as a burden to her family, same as her limp becomes a burden to herself. Because of her feeling of her limp itself, it has influenced her entire personality so she cannot be what her mother wants her to be.

LAURA. ... I won't come to the table.

AMNADA. What sort of nonsense is this? ... it won't be him! ... but whether it is or not, you will come to the table. You will not be excused.

[William in Dell Pub. Co., 1956:479, Scene Six]

Amanda wants Laura to greet her gentleman caller and be a lady at the dinnertime. But Laura gets very nervous when she knows that it is Jim who will arrives as her gentleman caller. She begs her mother to be excused from the table, and Amanda directly prohibits her daughter to be excused from their dinnertime that night, because as a young lady she should greet her gentleman caller and uses that chance to show her charm and vivacity to attract Mr. O'Connor.

Gender Analysis

Amanda becomes the primary socializer agent in patriarchal society, since she has adopted patriarchal values and has adopted societal standards on male and female members of the society and socializes the gender roles to her children. As the socializer agent, she divides the household responsibilities to her children based on their sexual differences. Amanda treats her children differently according to the societal standards, and gives sanctions to her children's behavior according to societal standards of what behaviors are appropriate and what are not regarding their position in the family and the society. Amanda emphasizes the traditional role of woman in the society to her daughter Laura that a woman should marry a gentleman one day, but notice that she does not do the same to her son Tom. It can be interpreted that in Amanda's society, the tendency for a young lady to marry someday is stronger than the tendency for a young man to marry somebody. It means that women in the society at that time have a great dependency on male figure, in order to survive in the society and able to take care of her self and her family.

As the socializer agent, Amanda also socializes several traditional roles to her daughter Laura as a young lady: a young lady should always stay fresh and pretty for gentleman callers; a young lady should master the art of conversation to attract and to entertain young men; a young lady should become a pretty trap for the gentleman callers; a young lady should have an attractive, charming, and vivacious nature; and a young lady should occupy a position in society, especially as a secretary (by mastering typewriting and shorthand skills). During this process of gender role socialization, Amanda often gives negative sanctions to her daughter either in form of facial expression, negative words and sentences, and prohibition if Laura's behaviors do not accomplish her standard of Laura's behaviors.

The great dependency on the male figure in this play implies also in the description of the ways in which Amanda treats her children in decision-making. During this play, it can be said that Amanda never asks Laura about her dreams of life, or her plans for the future. The conversation between Amanda and Laura is more like one-way conversation, meaning that Amanda determines what is best for Laura's life in the future first and then says it to Laura, rather than discusses it first with her daughter. In their conversation, Amanda only advises her daughter about what a young lady should do and should become in society. On the other hand, it can be seen that Amanda and Tom often have a quarrel about Tom's behavior and opinion about his position in the Warehouse, and about Tom's ambition to be a writer and an adventurer. Actually their quarrel describes the interaction between Amanda and her son, if it compares to the conversation between Amanda and Laura. Based on these facts described in the play, it can be interpreted that in the family, Amanda shows her great dependency on the male figure by trusting her son Tom to help her in making decisions. For example, the discussion for Laura's next life in the future is only happened between Amanda and Tom. Amanda only discusses about their family life and her plans for her children's future with Tom instead of involving Laura, though Laura is two years older than Tom. It might be caused by Laura's inferior nature, but it also might be caused by Tom's position in the family is higher than Laura, concerning that Tom replaces his father's position as a partner of Amanda in discussion and decision-making, though at last it still Amanda who makes all decisions in the family.

CONCLUSION

There are two important messages conveyed in this play. The first message is the 'destiny' of female in society to become a housewife and focus on domesticity. It has been clearly socialized by Amanda to Laura in form of the kinds of gender roles and the ways of these gender roles are socialized. The second message is the dependency on the male character/s by the female character/s. The author here emphasizes on the dependency of the female characters on three male figures. First, Amanda always blames her husband who had deserted her many years ago as a cause of their family bankruptcy. This can be interpreted as the dependency on the husband figure who has a responsibility to maintain financial security of the family also as the guardian for the family. Second, is the presence of a Gentleman Caller, Mr. O'Connor. Amanda has the great expectation on this gentleman; marry her daughter Laura and then support the financial security of the Wingfield family. Unfortunately, Mr. O'Connor here fails to fulfill Amanda's hope and ambition, because he is already engaged with someone else, and therefore he ruins Laura's life and breaks it at the same time. It can be interpreted that Laura still needs a male figure to help her to realize that she is actually has an interesting inner charm and vivacious nature, but at the same time, this male figure causes her spirit to live a normal life like other ladies and to find a normal husband, falls into pieces. Third, Amanda shows her great dependency on Tom, starting from supporting the financial security of the family, until finding the best husband for Laura. Again, this

expectation also fails because Tom at last chooses his personal ambition, and leaves his family for a new adventure. All the conditions above show that the female characters in this play have a great dependency on male figure. They still need male figure as a breadwinner and a guardian in the family, also as a 'hero' for an unmarried young lady, to help them survive in the society.

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